

Innovation Management in Living Lab projects: the Innovatrix Framework

Dimitri Schuurman¹, Aron-Levi Herregodts*¹,
Annabel Georges¹, Olivier Rits¹

*Corresponding author
¹ imec.livinglabs

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Abstract

Despite being described as ‘orchestrators’ and innovation intermediaries, the Living Labs literature on concrete guidelines and tools for innovation project-related innovation management is scant. Within this paper, we propose the Innovatrix, an innovation management framework built upon existing business model and innovation management tools and frameworks and iterated based on practical experience in Living Lab projects. We illustrate its added value within three practical case studies that lead to three propositions regarding innovation management in Living Lab projects. First, Innovatrix helps to scope the user involvement activities, which leads to a more efficient use of resources. Second, Innovatrix forces the project owner to focus on a limited number of customer segments, which increases the efficient spending of the scarce entrepreneurial resources. Third, Innovatrix allows to capture the iterations and pivots that were made during an innovation project, which helps to link outcomes with certain Living Lab activities.

Keywords: *Living Labs; Innovation Management; Business Modeling; User research; Assumption; Validation; Testing.*

1 Introduction

Although we seem to be living in an era where founding a start-up company has never been easier, studies point out to high mortality rates of these organizations. A Harvard Business School study put forwards a failure rate of 75% (Gage, 2012), whereas a CB Insight study even proposes 90% for digital innovations (CB Insights, 2018). This pleads for more research and insights into innovation management and innovation intermediaries that can help these failure rates go down. One specific type of innovation intermediary are the so-called Living Labs.

Living labs are complex partnerships, as they facilitate university-industry relationships but also relationships between large companies, SMEs and startups. Living Labs are often referred to as public- private-people partnerships (4P's) (Westerlund and Leminen, 2011). Based on a meta-review of the Living Labs literature, Schuurman (2015) defines Living Labs as an organized approach (as opposed to an ad hoc approach) to innovation consisting of real-life experimentation and active user involvement by means of different methods involving multiple stakeholders, as is implied in the Public-Private-People character of Living Labs. Moreover, he also concludes that Living Labs are emanations of both Open Innovation and User Innovation practices, as external inputs, including end-user contributions, are used to iteratively design and cocreate the innovation in development. This opening of the innovation process and the involvement of external actors in a structural process have the potential to increase the value and sustainability of the business model of the innovation (Baccarne et al., 2013). However, there is only a limited amount of literature available that combine Living Labs with business models. Rits et al. (2015) note that the majority of the papers in this field deal with the business model of Living Labs themselves, but that explicit integration of business model research in Living Labs is very rare. Moreover, in his literature review of the most influential Living Lab papers, Schuurman (2015) discovered that the majority dealt with the Living Lab organizations. This feels contra-intuitive as Living Labs are regarded as innovation instruments and innovation intermediaries that are capable of closing the gap between research and market introduction (Almirall & Wareham, 2011). Therefore, we would expect much more attention for the Living Lab project activities, and practical guidelines how to approach innovation projects in a Living Lab setting. In this paper, we focus on this project level and look for innovation management guidelines in Living Labs. After a review of Living Labs literature, we propose the Innovatrix framework, based on existing innovation management and business model tools and frameworks. We then investigate the practical implementation of Innovatrix by means of four case studies, selected from a sample of 40 Living Lab projects that used the Innovatrix framework.

Innovation management in Living Labs

Living Labs are regarded as complex phenomena where three analytical levels can be distinguished: the organizational level, the project level and the individual user interactions level (Schuurman, 2015). The defining elements of Living Labs, real-life context, multi-stakeholder, multi-method, active user co-creation and medium- to long term (Schuurman et al., 2013), are situated among these three separate, but interlinked layers. The multi-stakeholder characteristic especially applies to the organizational level. In this domain, Leminen (2015) provides a very diverse overview of actor roles and management implications for Living Lab networks. Managing value capture and value creation processes within Living Lab organizations is crucial for their sustainability, but also cumbersome (Schaffers et al., 2007). This also resonates with the medium- to long-term element. On the user interactions level, end-user co-creation is regarded as the way to involve users. The literature describes various ways and strategies to facilitate the process of co-creation (e.g. Kristensson et al., 2008) and provides an overview of different user characteristics and user roles (Leminen et al., 2014; Schuurman & De Marez, 2012) of Living Lab participants.

In terms of the project level, the real-life aspect and the multi-method approach are characteristics. There is some literature on the real-life aspect and on context (e.g. Bergvall-Kåreborn et al., 2009). The other element is the multi-method nature of Living Lab projects. These Living Lab projects are described as a structured approach to open and user innovation (Almirall & Wareham, 2008; Leminen et al., 2012; Schuurman et al., 2016). This way, we look at Living Lab projects from an innovation management perspective. However, Living Lab papers on methodology tend to describe a very specific methodology, which is specific for a certain Living Lab, or an innovation process with rather fixed elements and building blocks (e.g. Bergvall-Kåreborn et al., 2010). The most concrete are the works of Pierson and Lievens (2005) and Schuurman et al. (2016) who put forward a quasi-experimental design, with a pre-test, an intervention and a post-test. Next to this, there is little to no literature that looks at innovation management in Living Lab projects, with the exception of some studies on 'Living-Labs-as-a-service' (see the next section). This is surprising, as already in 2006, at the start of the Living Labs movement, Niitamo et al. state that "[i]n Living Labs there is a need to combine highly self-organized and self-managed processes with multi-disciplinary R&D and innovation management processes". Ståhlbröst (2013) also defines a Living Lab as "an orchestrator of open innovation processes focusing on co-creation of innovations in real-world contexts by involving multiple stakeholders with the objective to generate sustainable value for all stakeholders focusing in particular on the end users". Nonetheless, this has not led to an abundance of papers and studies that unravel or describe this process of orchestration. Coupled to this lack of innovation management guidelines for Living Lab projects, there are only few studies

that present concrete results of the outcomes of Living Lab projects, and even fewer that compare Living Lab projects with other innovation projects. Ballon et al. (2018) relate this to the complexity of the Living Labs phenomenon, but also urge for more studies in this domain. Therefore, within this paper, we will propose a tool that can be used as innovation management approach and that also enables to elicitate impact and outcomes of Living Lab interventions.

2 Business model components as innovation management elements

A notable exception of the search for innovation management anchor points for Living Labs can be found in the scant literature on Living-Labs-As-A-Service. These Living Labs, focused on delivering specific services to external customers, play the role of innovation intermediary between entrepreneurs and end-users (Ståhlbröst, 2013). Coorevits and Schuurman (2014) argue that the Validation board (leanstartupmachine.com), from the Lean Start-up methodology, can be used as a tool to structure Living Lab projects as it is focused on planning and executing user research. Rits et al. (2015) argue for the integration of business model research with user research in Living Labs. In this context, they refer to established tools linked to business modeling and technology entrepreneurship, such as the Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2013), the Lean Canvas (Maurya, 2012), and the Value Proposition Canvas (Osterwalder, Pigneur, Bernarda & Smith, 2015). D'Hauwers et al. (2015) proposed the iLLAB, a hypothesis driven Living Lab framework incorporating both user and business model learning, based on elements from the above business model tools. They see the iLLAB tool as an aggregation of principles from Ries (2011), the Osterwalder Value Proposition Design (2015), the business model matrix of Ballon (2007), the business model canvas of Osterwalder (2010) and Porter's five forces model (1985) and translated into a set of strategic components. They developed their own framework to gather assumptions for user research, as the input from the other frameworks remained too high-level to define and execute user research. The validation board (Ries, 2011) functioned as main framework as it puts the customers at the core and focuses on customer hypothesis, problem hypothesis and solution hypothesis. This is also in line with the work of Wildevuur et al. (2013) who designed the People Value Canvas (PVC) tool to help build value propositions during user-centric service development processes. The PVC consists of nine building blocks, describing the input that has to be provided to establish the value proposition. The PVC is an iteration on the business model canvas. This facilitates a process-oriented approach, more specifically for highly iterative (and lean) innovation processes allowing for structured learning and pivoting.

However, based on practical experience with the validation board and the iLLAB-tool, we felt that more structure could be added to the existing elements. This is acknowledged by Herregodts et al. (2017) who develop a framework on knowledge uncertainties. Within these uncertainties, a major distinction can be made between knowledge related to the current environment versus knowledge related to the innovation under development. While the first is closely related to problem and opportunity identification, the second is related to the formulation and evaluation of solutions. This framework is based on the metaphoric use of 'states'. States relate to reference points, either from the perspective of the organization or the individual (Gourville, 2005). Where the existing, 'current state of being', the 'as-is' or 'status quo' is opposing 'possible future states' (Alasoini, 2011). These insights led to the Innovatrix- framework (figure 1), which used elements from the previously discussed frameworks and tools, but that also considers this dichotomy between current and future state-knowledge. This resonates with a more process-oriented approach and should facilitate innovation management in an optimal way. We now briefly introduce and discuss the elements that compose the Innovatrix: customer segment, current practices, needs, value proposition, solution, barriers, value capture & key partners. The eight components will be discussed in more detail.

INNOVATRIX imec.livinglabs ASSUMPTION & VALIDATION MATRIX		imec		
CUSTOMER SEGMENT				
NEEDS				
CURRENT PRACTICES				
VALUE PROPOSITION				
SOLUTION				
BARRIERS				
VALUE CAPTURE				
KEY PARTNERS				

Figure 1. Innovatrix assumption & validation matrix

Customer segment – Current state

As used in the Validation Board (Ries, 2011) and the Business Model Canvas, Innovatrix starts from customer segments. However, there is room for multiple customer segments and the other elements are all linked to customer segments, and do not necessarily apply for all segments. This enables more fine-grained assumption development. In the Innovatrix framework there's room for three customer segments (the grey areas in the framework) to cater to the need of clear focus through limited scope. The first column is used as an overarching column to map similarities between defined segments. Following Innovatrix checks can be used to gauge for relevant input to the Customer Segment criteria: *What customer segments to focus on? What are key characteristics? What is the use-context?*

Needs – Current state

Osterwalder (2015) includes customer jobs, pains, and gains in the Value Proposition Design canvas, which is the basis for the needs identification in the Innovatrix framework. Furthermore, Ries (2011) links customer segments - customer problems and the fit with the potential solution and/or value proposition. Following Innovatrix checks can be used to gauge for relevant input to the Needs criteria: *What are the needs of the customer segment? How do we prioritise these needs?*

Current practices – Current state

One missing pillar in Ries (2011), Osterwalder (2010) and in Ballon (2007), is the competition and the differentiation of an SME/start-up/innovator. Competition refers to the Five Market Forces of Porter (1985), which draws from five forces model. The five forces make up the attractiveness of a market. The five forces can be defined as (1) rivalry within the industry, (2) threat of new entrants, (3) the threat of substitutes, (4) bargaining power of suppliers and, (5) bargaining power of buyers. Assessing the rivalry within the industry can help identify the difficulties of entering the market. If for example, the market consists of multiple strong players (i.e., Oligopoly market), the need to diversify can lead to high barriers to entry. On the other hand, if several new entrants enter the market (Monopolistic competition), it could indicate that it's an attractive market with lower barriers of entry. For some products and/or services one can find possible substitutes, which can serve as an alternative to the specific service and/or product. Following Innovatrix checks can be used to gauge for relevant input to the Current Practices criteria: *Who or what are competitors, alternatives, customer behaviour? What are the pains and gains of these current practices?*

Value proposition – Current & future state

The value proposition is covered by the Lean Matrix of Ries (2011), the Value Proposition and the Business Model Canvas of Osterwalder (2010,2015) and, by the Business Model Matrix of Ballon (2007). The value proposition is the match between the needs of customer segments, and how this can be solved with the solution provided by the innovator. Following Innovatrix check can be used to gauge for relevant input to the Value Proposition criteria: *What (measurable) impact will you create for this customer segment?*

Solution – Future state

The solution refers to ‘the functional architecture’ of Ballon in the Business Model Matrix (2007). The functional architecture comprises of the technical systems composed of at least one building block (or module), governed by specific rules (or intelligence) that interwork (or not) with other technical systems through predetermined interfaces. The composition of the solution in the key modules and technical systems enables the researcher and the innovator to identify the unique selling point of the innovation compared to the competition. This division is less explicitly included in Osterwalder (2010), even though the difference can be significant in certain innovations. Following Innovatrix checks can be used to gauge for relevant input to the Solution criteria: What are the components of your (digital) solution? How do these components differ for the different customer segments?

Barriers – Future state

According to Steinkühler, Mahlendorf & Brettel (2014) self-justification is the most empirically supported explanation for escalation of commitment, the “...tendency to become locked-in to a course of action, throwing good money after bad or committing new resources to a losing course of action” (Staw, 1981). Therefore, Steinkühler and his colleagues (2014) argue that self-justification cannot be totally avoided but for de-escalation of the commitments, the search for disconfirming evidence can help. Therefore, it was decided to explicitly include ‘barriers’ as an element to look for this disconfirming evidence. Following Innovatrix checks can be used to gauge for relevant input to the Barriers criteria: What are the barriers for adoption, usage and market entry?

Value Capture – Future state

Ballon (2007) included the financial model in the Business Model Matrix, which described the revenue model and the revenue sharing model. Osterwalder (2010) also considers the revenues model, where the pricing level and the pricing model are mentioned. The researchers opted to utilize the definition of ‘Value capture’, which

comprises of the pricing model and the pricing level, and in cases where revenue sharing is applicable, this section can be utilized. The application of the Innovatrix matrix in different projects shows that partners can face difficulties identifying their pricing model and pricing level, and thus this needs to be included in the Innovatrix matrix. It is important to note that Value capturing has an important link with how pressing the customer need is, and to the associated value the partner promises to deliver. Following Innovatrix checks can be used to gauge for relevant input to the Value Capture criteria: *What value (monetary and non-monetary) do I receive in return? What price should I set (and how)?*

Key Partners – Future state

The value network definition is an alternative to the broad market-based approach of the Business Model Matrix of Ballon (2007). In the value network analysis, though the applicability is more adapted to innovations in the form of partnerships required to deliver the innovation to the customers and with whom do innovators need to collaborate. Following Innovatrix checks can be used to gauge for relevant input to the Key Partners criteria: *Who are your key partners? How to interact with stakeholders?*

3 Innovatrix put to practice: from workshop to innovation management process

In practice, the Innovatrix is used twofold: 1) as an innovation framework in a hands-on workshop session and 2) as an innovation management process.

First, as an innovation framework, the Innovatrix is used at the start of an innovation project, during a kick-off workshop. The most important roles in such a workshop are the trained Innovatrix facilitator and the innovator (or the innovator's team). The workshop starts with an innovation pitch provided by the innovator. After this pitch, the eight distinctive Innovatrix criteria – as described above – are 'filled' with relevant input from the innovator. Here, the facilitator plays an important role in the gathering of all relevant input through the means of very specific probing questions in the form of 'Innovatrix checks'. The gathered input is then awarded one of initially two possible statuses, based on the nature and the strength of the input: either assumption (the input has not yet been validated and is thus hypothesized by the innovator) or validated assumption (the input has already been validated in previous activities). Depending on the assumption status, the input is mapped on different-coloured post-its: yellow (assumptions) or green (validated assumptions). The outcome of an Innovatrix workshop is the mapping of assumptions and validated

assumptions, followed by marking the most important assumptions as 'key uncertainties'. The focus of following research activities should then put on these key uncertainties.

Second, the Innovatrix is used as support of the innovation management process. Here, the the Innovatrix framework is used as the starting point of a living lab innovation project. The outcome of the Innovatrix workshop, key uncertainties, is then translated into testable assumptions and matched with adequate research and innovation activities. Research and innovation activities are then carried out. In a next Innovatrix workshop, the Innovatrix update, the focus is placed on these key uncertainties that were object of research and innovation activities. Here, the assumption status is under debate based on the outputs of the research and innovation activities. In an Innovatrix update, the status of an assumption can be changed in dialogue with the entrepreneur with following possible statuses: assumption (the research has not been validated), validated assumption (the input was validated), new insight (new information arose from the research and innovation activities) and invalidated (the assumption proof to be invalidated). The Innovatrix is thus used in support of the innovation management process through the mapping and changing of assumption statuses in a structured dialogue with the innovator throughout the entire living lab innovation project. This process is repeated until the end of the living lab project.

4 Methodology

Within this paper, we adopt a mixed design with quantitative and qualitative data. For the quantitative part, we look at all innovation projects carried out by the user research team of imec.livinglabs from 2011 up till 2018, which makes for a sample of 86 projects. For this sample we coded whether Innovatrix was used or not, based on the project deliverables. In practice, the older projects did not use Innovatrix, whereas the more recent projects all made use of Innovatrix. We also coded the status of the project in terms of project outcome: 'on the market' if the innovation is available for adoption by end-users, 'abort' if the innovation project is stopped and the team members disband, 'reboot' if the innovation project is stopped, but the team members continue with a new innovation project, based on the insights, and 'in development' is used to indicate that the innovation is not launched yet. This can be regarded as an 'in between' category, as over time these projects will either become available on the market, be aborted or be rebooted. The data for the initial coding of the projects is taken from a post assessment interview at the end of the project. However, every year this database is updated based on an online search and a personal follow-up with the project owners to assess changes. The last update of the status dates from May 2018.

All of these projects were innovations with a digital component. The majority (58) had a focus on B2C, whereas the remaining 28 projects could be labelled as B2B. For an idea of some of the projects, see Schuurman (2015) and Schuurman et al. (2016).

For the quantitative analysis, we simply compared the numbers of the projects with Innovatrix and the (older) ones without Innovatrix (see Table 1). Because of the relatively small sample size, as compared to the outcome categories, no chi-square tests could be performed as the expected cell numbers were less than 5 for more than 20% of the cells. Therefore, we simply report the percentages. For the qualitative study, we selected cases where the Innovatrix had explicit value. These cases were chosen after a review of all projects by the co-authors, so the cases can be considered as illustrative case studies (Yin, 2017).

5 Results

The dataset consisted of in total 86 entrepreneurial innovation projects. Almost half made use of Innovatrix, whereas 46 projects did not use the framework. When we look at the outcomes over all, we already see a few striking results. Roughly 1 out of 4 of the projects is stopped after the project and almost 1 out of 10 is rebooted based on the project insights, whereas 1 out of 10 is still 'in development' or implementing the lessons learned. However, it is remarkable that almost 60% ends up in a market launch. Referring back to the CB Insights study, where only 10% made in to the market, the type of projects is rather different. In that study, entrepreneurs from an incubator were studied, whereas in our study, the entrepreneurs should be considered as more mature as they contacted an innovation intermediary (our Living Lab) for support, defined a project proposal and paid for the project. However, this big difference is still remarkable.

Table 1

Status	Living Lab projects without Innovatrix	Living Lab projects with Innovatrix	Overall
Abort	N: 19 – 41%	2 – 5%	N: 21 – 24%
Reboot	N: 5 – 11%	2 – 5%	N: 7 – 8%
In development	N: 0 – 9%	9 – 23%	N: 9 – 10%
On the market	N: 22 – 48%	27 – 67%	N/ 49 – 57%
Total	N: 46 – 53%	N: 40 – 47%	N: 86

As we look to the split between projects with and without Innovatrix, there are quite some interesting differences as well. Only two projects were aborted, whereas in the non-Innovatrix sample this is over 40%. Also, the percentage of reboots is also half as high in the Innovatrix-category. All of the projects that are still ‘in development’ belong to the Innovatrix category, which illustrates the point that this is a ‘transit’ category because over time all projects end up in one of the other categories. Finally, in this data set, two out of three innovation project that used innovatrix during their Living Lab project resulted in a market launch. As a lot of these projects were finished quite recently, these numbers will undoubtedly change, but still this contrasts heavily with the 9/10 failure ratio.

We now turn over to three case studies where Innovatrix was used and provided specific value to the innovation project.

Motosmarty. This project was about a mobile application that detected the driving behaviour of young people in order to give feedback and assess their risk profile. In term of end-user focus, there were no issues as the target population were young people and students. Co-creation sessions, surveys and user tests were performed to iterate the application. However, in terms of customer segment for the generated data of the application, there was no focus at all. Here, the Innovatrix was used to explicate all knowledge and assumptions regarding these customer segments (17 in total!). This led to discussions inside the team and made them realize that focus was needed, otherwise they would burn all their resources without finding a paying (B2B) customer. They are now on the market as Road Skippers and as Smart Drivers and focus on insurance companies.

Spott. This Living Lab project was about a new way to recognize, like, share and buy products with your smartphone based on what you see during a TV show or TV commercial. The Innovatrix workshop at the start of the project indicated three types of end-user segments and the television stations. In terms of value capture, the assumption was that an affiliate marketing fee was the main source of income for Spott. However, based on the co-creation sessions and field trials with the

application, it appeared that the 'buying' of items recognized during the TV-show was not that common, but that more adept TV viewers felt more connected to the TV content as they received more information on the objects that were used or worn by their favorite characters. This newly discovered evidence made Spott delete one of the end-user segments, that was focused on buying, and turned more towards the 'heavy' TV-viewers, with as main income TV station paying to use the application for their TV shows. The higher attraction of the content could attract advertisers, which made the application interesting for them and increased their willingness-to-pay. In this project, Innovatrix brought scope, identified unexpected outcomes and enabled to focus on a limited number of segments. At the moment, Spott has already been launched in multiple countries worldwide and is growing rapidly.

Lab Box: Lab Box is the organization behind Pikaway, a multi-modal transport application that is able to plan and book trips, and is not restricted to one or a few means of transport. At the starting workshop, it appeared that the three customer segments were still rather high level and in need of specification. To tackle this, we did a segmentation survey and subsequently conducted a field trial with representatives of the user segments. This enabled to create persona, which provided focus for the developers to prioritize their development backlog. Moreover, one of the key assumptions captured during the first workshop, the need for a one-stop shop application, could be iteratively validated by capturing the frustrations with the current practices in the segmentation survey and co-creation session, but this was also expressed in the field trial so this was also reflected in the future state (solutions element). At the end of the project, the people from Lab Box asked for the main take-aways and next steps for them based on the project. By going through the Innovatrix and the modifications step by step, we could easily extract the main learnings and key elements to work on before the market launch. At this moment, Pikaway is available in the app store and a launch in the Play Store is planned for the near future.

6 Discussion & Conclusion

Although Living Labs are regarded as orchestrators, which hints at an innovation management approach, there is a lack of literature and studies that further explicate this role of the process. Rather, Living Labs are described and studied in terms of defining characteristics (such as real-life experimentation, active user co-creation and public-private-people partnership), but it is left untouched how these elements should be managed and utilized according to the needs and characteristics of a specific innovation project. For Living Labs to take the next step in becoming mature and established innovation organizations, we feel that this innovation management role should be further elaborated and that this is even crucial in the complex entities that Living Labs are. The three-layered model of Schuurman (2015) provides a

useful framework to anchor these elaborations. In our literature review, we noticed that the largest gap in terms of the orchestration role in Living Labs is situated on the project level. Therefore, within this paper we focused on the question how innovation management in Living Lab projects can be facilitated and supported by tools or frameworks.

As a result, we presented the Innovatrix framework, consisting of eight elements, derived from existing business model tools and frameworks, with as specific characteristic the fact that all elements of the framework should be specified for each customer segment that is identified. Moreover, the Innovatrix also has a clear distinction between the current state elements (the top three) and the future state elements (the bottom four), which gives it a more dynamic, process-like feeling.

Based on an analysis of 86 Living Lab projects, where just over half did not use Innovatrix and just under half did use Innovatrix, we discovered that two out of three projects using Innovatrix resulted in a market launch. More data is needed to validate these findings, but this gives a first indication of the effectiveness of the framework. Moreover, based on three illustrative case studies of projects from the sample that used innovatrix, we can derive three propositions regarding the use and implications of the Innovatrix framework.

First, Innovatrix helps to scope the user involvement activities, as it clearly explicates assumptions, related to the different customer segments, and it also enables indicating which assumptions are key for taking the next steps in the project. This leads to a more efficient use of resources and facilitates the selection of representative users for the given customer segments and also guides the choice of method to validate the assumption.

Second, Innovatrix forces the project owner to focus on a limited number of customer segments, as there is only room for three to four segments maximum. If there are more segments, the elements of the Innovatrix help to choose between different segments in terms of focus. This increases the efficient spending of the scarce entrepreneurial resources and helps decision making for the innovation teams. Third, Innovatrix allows to capture the iterations and pivots that were made during an innovation project. This is especially useful to link outcomes with certain Living Lab activities, as this has appeared rather problematic to this date (see Ballon et al., 2018). Innovatrix serves as a visual summary of key elements and assumptions regarding an innovation project from the viewpoint of the end-user. By capturing snapshots of its state before and after a research activity, the modifications and alterations become apparent. To this end, at the moment a digital version of Innovatrix is being built that enables to fill out Innovatrix digitally and keep track of all changes during a project. Moreover, Innovatrix is also an interesting tool to facilitate the discussion between Living Lab researchers and the project owners.

To further explore and validate these propositions, more research is needed and more cases are needed to assess the value of Innovatrix. Also, Innovatrix represent a specific view on innovation management and Living Lab activities. It has been used in a 'Living-Labs-as-a-service'-context, but might be applicable in other contexts as well. We encourage uses and tests in other contexts, other types of projects and other organizations in order to increase the knowledge on innovation management in a Living Lab-context and to help building a more structural, encompassing Innovatrix for all kinds of Living Lab projects and activities to increase the impact and position of Living Labs as innovation intermediaries.

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